

LYMPHADENITIS CAUSES, SYMPTOMS, DIAGNOSIS, TREATMENT, LYMPHADENITIS IN CHILDREN

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Abstract: this thesis deals with lymphadenitis disease, clinical symptoms and modern methods of treatment.

Key words: specific and nonspecific, thrombophlebitis, syphilis, gonorrhea

Lymphadenitis is a pathology characterized by specific or nonspecific inflammation of lymph nodes. During its development, the enlargement of lymph nodes, pain during palpation and general weakness are observed. the cause of inflammation is infection. The nature of the causative agent and the level of its sensitivity to antibiotics are determined in the analysis of the biopsy sample taken from the damaged nodes. On the background of lymphadenitis, purulent complications — abscesses or adenophlegmons — may develop. such furnaces must be opened and drained.

In the initial stages, the enlargement of the lymph nodes occurs. Stable hyperemia (blood accumulation) develops. Serous absorption of nodular tissue is noted. Leukocytes actively migrate to the site of injury and proliferative cell growth begins in the lymphoid tissue. All pathological changes are localized in the capsule. In catarrhal and hyperplastic forms, infectious inflammation can become chronic. In the further development of the pathology, the lymph node is affected by purulent dissolution with the formation of a purulent focus. Abscess appears (limited pus accumulation in the capsule). Its contents can fall into the area of cells, which leads to the development of adenophlegmon and the spread of the inflammatory process to the surrounding tissues - paralympadenitis.

Necrotic type of parology develops in rapid and massive necrosis of lymph nodes.

Fibrinous lymphadenitis is characterized by the formation of fibrin clots in parallel with the release of a large amount of exudate.

In dangerous infectious diseases such as plague and anthrax, lymph nodes are infiltrated with blood. In such cases, the hemorrhagic form of lymphadenitis is mentioned.

Lymphadenitis is usually a consequence of primary septic inflammation. Pathogenic (pyogenic) microflora — streptococci and staphylococci and the toxins they produce migrate from the focus with the lymphogenous route or blood flow. Infectious agents can also enter the lymphatic vessels through injured skin or mucous membranes (contact route).

Primary furnaces can be:

- Bone panaritsii;
- Infected wounds;
- Boils and carbuncles;
- Serous inflammation;
- Abscesses;
- Inflammation of bone and bone marrow (osteomyelitis).

One of the common reasons for the development of lymphadenitis is dental diseases, including dental caries. A chronic focus of infection can support the inflammatory process for a long time.

Pathology often also occurs against the background of thrombophlebitis.

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